

Edge Impulse and TinyML: An Integrated Solution for Weed Classification

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Summary– The application of herbicides in agriculture to control the growth of weeds triggers several problems, such as contamination of the water table and plantations, economic losses, environmental risks, and damage to health. Thus, TinyML appears as a solution for controlling the growth of weedy plants. The objective of this work is to develop a weed image classifier and, from there, reduce the use of herbicides.

Keywords: TinyML; Image classifier; Herbicides; Weedy plants; Plantations.

INTRODUCTION

Future expectations show that water and food will be among the main dilemmas for humanity in the next 50 years [1]. Brazil's agriculture is considered highly competitive, and the country is among the largest producers and suppliers of food on the planet, according to the Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock, and Supply (MAPA) [2][3]. The sector is responsible for 43.2% of the country's exports, and grain production alone reached approximately 232.6 million tons, according to 2020 data from the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE) [3].

With the growth of agriculture over recent years, the use of agricultural pesticides to combat pests or weedy plants continues to increase. Soybean, corn, and sugarcane plantations alone account for 75% of the agricultural pesticides consumed in the country, according to data from the National Union of the Plant Defense Products Industry (Sindiveg) [4][5]. The excessive use of pesticides causes harmful damage to groundwater and surface water, soil contamination, environmental impacts, and affects human health. Furthermore, there is also the possibility of resistance in some weedy plants, that is, herbicides not being able to combat pests. [5][6]. According to 2017 United Nations (UN) data, approximately 200,000 people, mostly rural workers, die yearly from acute pesticide poisoning. It is estimated that between 2007 and 2015 in Brazil, around 84.2 thousand cases of poisoning following exposure to agricultural pesticides, according to a report from the Ministry of Health.

Among the pesticides used in plantations, herbicides stand out in the control of weeds, considered invasive and weedy plants [4]. Weeds are direct competitors of planted crops, competing for natural resources such as water, sun, and nutrients. The weeds are predisposed to adapt and develop in environments with varied conditions [7]. According to the Brazilian Agricultural Research Corporation (Embrapa), weeds harm the quality, generate harvest losses, and cause a 13% to 15% deficit in grain production. Fig.1 shows plant management to control weed proliferation. The weeds are eliminated throughout the critical moment of competition and thus do not compete with the planted crops [7]. Digital agriculture offers technological solutions, for example, image processing and computer vision, to contribute to the classification of

pests, and such techniques are already used in detecting and inspecting food quality [2].

Based on this information, the objective of this article is to develop an image classifier of weeds and thus alert direct workers to the presence of these unwanted plants and contribute to faster and more assertive decision-making to eliminate weeds from plantations during the critical period of competition and reducing the use of herbicides. To develop the classifier, the Edge Impulse platform we use to carry out the AI application and, using Tiny Machine Learning (TinyML) techniques, enable the use of Artificial Intelligence on devices with little processing capacity and low cost.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Below are some strategies and related works, and we present the tools and proposals developed in the article.

A. Weeds and the Use of Herbicides

Weeds in agriculture occur due to several effects that directly affect the planted crop. For example, the high interference about competition for natural resources, difficulty harvesting, and hosting pests and diseases harm the product's quality. Weeds, unlike other pests, have many species, and because they appear at any time of the year, they make it difficult to control their growth and spread [7].

Figure 1 – Control of weeds between soybean rows. [10]

Weed development occurs under adverse conditions, and because weeds exhibit competitive behavior, they multiply and ensure their continuation through dormancy and non-uniformity in seed twinning. Furthermore, the infestation of invasive

plants such as weeds in plantations devalues the commercial price of the environment [10].

The losses caused by herbicides on the planet correspond to an average of 19 billion dollars. In Brazil alone, between 2006 and 2007, spending on herbicides to control weeds was approximately 1.7 billion dollars [7].

B. Herbicide Resistance

The preference for using herbicides to control weed proliferation is because it is a more practical solution when compared to other control methods. However, weeds resistant to this agricultural pesticide have emerged due to the excessive use of herbicides. Thus, the yield in crops decreases, the cost of production increases, and results in the restriction of some herbicides as they no longer have any effect on eliminating weeds [10].

The resistance of a weed plant to a herbicide is the acquired ability to continue its survival and reproduction, even after application of the herbicide at the recommended dose and under normal and appropriate application conditions. According to information from Embrapa, soybean crops that face weeds resistant to glyphosate, the primary herbicide consumed in Brazil, showed an increase in costs ranging from 22% to 42%. According to data from the leading pesticide producer Syngenta, 60% of the total soybean area planted has weeds resistant to herbicides in Brazil. The cost of eliminating resistant weeds is around 9 billion reais and the possibility of causing losses of up to 70% if no control is established [4].

C. TinyML

TinyML is the technology that integrates machine learning and embedded systems, enabling intelligent applications in low-energy devices. These devices have memory and processing capacity limitations but can collect data from the physical environment through sensors and act based on machine learning algorithms' decisions [8]. TinyML can solve fundamental Internet of Things (IoT) device issues, such as bandwidth and latency constraints. Traditional IoT devices send data and delegate algorithm-intensive tasks to cloud services. With TinyML technology, there is no need to transfer data to third parties, ensuring information privacy [9].

D. Edge Impulse

Edge Impulse is an online tool created to make collecting data, training deep learning models, and deploying these models on embedded and edge computing devices simpler, allowing us to quickly address the previously mentioned issues, as shown in Fig. 2 [15].

Figure 2 – Process carried out by Edge Impulse [15].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A computer, a smartphone, the Edge Impulse platform, and a data set were needed to develop the image classifier. The acquired dataset or image bank was made available by the Kaggle platform [12], which has several directories. The classifier proposed in the work must identify weeds in plantations, so we used a dataset of weeds and another of soybeans [13][14].

Edge Impulse received 680 image files, 543 images for training and 137 for testing the developed model, separated into two classes, one called "Weeds" and the other "Soy." Figure 3 presents the image classifier model.

Figure 3 – Edge Impulse Platform Impulse Screen. Source: Authors (2023)

Fig. 4 shows the Neural Network Architecture used and the parameters adjusted for the classifier model, with the input layer, use of 32 filters, 16 filters, Flatten layer, and dropout rate 0.25. According to the label given at the images' input, the classifier has two outputs, "Weeds" and "Soy." Thus, after several iterations, the neural network learns and starts to predict actions more assertively.

Figure 4 – Architecture of the Neural Network used. Source: Authors (2023)

After being trained and validated, the model was included in a kit developed by Edge Impulse in partnership with Arduino for the "Edge Impulse University" program and made available to some

educational institutions worldwide. The program is an initiative to train teachers in TinyML to train students in using AI in edge-embedded systems. Fig. 5 shows the kit consisting of the Arduino Nano 33 BLE Sense Lite board, Arduino Tiny Machine Learning Shield, and the ArduCam OV7675 Camera [15].

Figure 5 – ML hardware kit [15].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results we obtained in the experiment were satisfactory.

After acquiring data from the Kaggle platform, uploading the image bank to the Edge Impulse platform, and creating the neural network model for the image classifier, model tests were carried out, evaluating the accuracy and confusion matrix and thus evaluating the results obtained and validating the model. Fig. 6 shows the accuracy and confusion matrix results obtained after training the model.

Figure 6 – Accuracy results and confusion matrix of the developed model.
 Source: Authors (2023)

We observe that the performance accuracy of the generated model is high, around 97.1%, which indicates good performance. Furthermore, the "Data explorer" showed the form of a spatial distribution where most of the data was correctly classified, where

the light green color indicates the correct classification of "Weeds" and dark green that of "Soy." The Confusion Matrix presents the results of correct and incorrect answers. In this case, the values generated by this matrix proved excellent since the success rate for classifying "Weeds" was 97.1%, and for "Soy," the rate was 97.2%.

After this first evaluation, we tested the final classifier model. At this stage, all sample data is analyzed and classified. Thus, the "Model Test" accuracy was again high, 93.13%. The confusion matrix of this model classified 98.8% of the "Weed" plant data as correct, and "Soy" had 83.3% of the data classified as valid.

During actual testing of the model, the classifier performed well overall. The model managed to classify the weeds as initially intended; however, the classifier performed better in classifying more approximate images of weeds, while in images of plantations, the classifier varied between the undefined and weed states. The model also performed well for soybean classification but took longer to identify soybeans. Fig. 7 shows the model test results.

Figure 7 – Accuracy results and confusion matrix from tests of the developed model.
 Source: Authors (2023)

Fig. 8 shows the model used on a smartphone in a soybean plantation and the results in evaluating

"Weeds" and "Soja."

Figure 8 – Demonstration of the use of the classifier.
 Source: Authors (2023)

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CONCLUSION

The results of training the developed model were consistent when subjected to test data. Image classification tests using a smartphone were a faster way to test the model on a soybean farm and an adequate ability to classify weeds by image. Tests on the model, developed using the Edge Impulse platform, performed well in most classifications. From this, it is possible to contribute to reducing the use of herbicides in plantations.

Future development prospects include the construction of low-cost equipment when compared to the use of smartphones, to be used by farmers and farm employees, and with the potential of being attached to drones that would carry out visual inspection. An expansion of the project will be the implementation of image detection, where the Neural Network model can identify the primary diseases in soybean leaves.

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